

-1 (1r→3a)

CP103: MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931

+2 (1a2→3a1)

+1 (3r→1a)

-1 (1r→3a)

-2 (1a1→2a2)

CP124: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301

+2 (3r→2a)

+1 (1r→2a)

-2 (3r→1a)

CP136: MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091

CP139: MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331

+1 (3r→1a)

+2 (2a1→1a2)

+1 (1r→2a)

+1 (2a2→3a1)

+2 (2a1→1a2)

-2 (3a1→1a2)

Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 3. A graphical summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 101-156. The rest of the legend is the same as for Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 1.